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Main Achievements

- 1 RESCALE Architecture**
- 1** In the first year of the project, all RESCALE partners worked diligently towards developing the first complete architecture for the project. This initial architecture marks a crucial milestone as it paves the way for the development of the project's integrated prototype. The architecture not only showcases the core functionality of RESCALE but through it, stakeholders can envision the project's capabilities and assess the concepts and knowledge conveyed by the project. The 1st version of the high-level architecture, depicted in Figure 1, consists of several key components that serve as the foundation for the ongoing work and future iterations of the architecture.

RESCALE Tools

Most of the tools intended for use in RESCALE's initial prototype have already been developed, marking another important step towards realizing the project's integrated system. These tools include both RESCALE's static and dynamic code analyzers. The static analyzers perform a thorough review of the codebase, identifying potential vulnerabilities and areas for improvement early in the development cycle. Meanwhile, the dynamic analyzers offers real-time insights during execution.

RESCALE YouTube Video

The RESCALE project has also launched its 1st YouTube video, which introduces the project, outlines its objectives and presents the consortium behind its development. The video serves as a key communication tool to engage stakeholders and the wider public by offering a clear overview of the project's ambitions and collaborative approach. You can find it on RESCALE's YouTube channel: [Rescale Project](#).

Figure 1 RESCALE's 1st Complete Architecture

Meetings

In the first year of the project, RESCALE organized the following project meetings:

- Kick-off Meeting, Athens
- 1st Plenary Meeting, Limassol
- 2nd Plenary and Technical Meeting, Cork
- S&T meetings
- Consortium meetings

Deliverables

The following deliverables were submitted in the first year of the project:

- D1.1 – Project handbook including Quality Management Plan, Risk Assessment and IPR management
- D1.2 – Data Management Plan
- D2.1 – Use Case Specification (first version)
- D2.3 – Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification (first version)
- D2.5 – High Level Architecture (first version)
- D4.1 – Specification of the TBOM Structure
- D6.1 – Project Website

Publications

13 total publications have been submitted by RESCALE partners in the first year. An indicative list follows:

- Predictive Context-sensitive Fuzzing. <https://zenodo.org/records/10973406>
- Leaky Address Masking: Exploiting Unmasked Spectre Gadgets with Noncanonical Address Translation. <https://zenodo.org/records/11333085>
- Sticky Tags: Efficient and Deterministic Spatial Memory Error Mitigation using Persistent Memory Tags. <https://zenodo.org/records/11335217>
- InSpectre Gadget: Inspecting the residual attack surface of cross-privilege Spectre v2. <https://zenodo.org/records/13771606>
- SafeFetch: Practical Double-Fetch Protection with Kernel-Fetch Caching. <https://zenodo.org/records/13771642>
- GhostRace: Exploiting and Mitigating Speculative Race Conditions. <https://zenodo.org/records/13771348>
- iVault: Architectural Code Concealing Techniques to Protect Cryptographic Keys. <https://zenodo.org/records/12684479>

For more information about the project deliverables and publications, visit RESCALE's Zenodo community: [RESCALE Project](#)

Collaboration

RESCALE has established connections with [SYNAPSE](#) by carrying out introductory online meetings with presentations from both projects, initial discussions and exchange of views. The fields of potential collaboration that were proposed by RESCALE and SYNAPSE include joint meetings, events, activities, exchange of information and cooperation regarding available communication channels.

Events

RESCALE participated in the following events in first year:

- [DFRWS EU 2023 Zaragoza](#)
- [Global Cybersecurity Summit 2024](#)
- [Hardwear.io Netherlands 2023](#)
- [Hardwear.io Netherlands 2024](#)
- [Code BEAM Europe 2024](#)

RESCALE co-organized the:

- [4th International Workshop on Advances on Privacy Preserving Technologies and Solutions](#)

ARES

IWAPS

4th International Workshop on Advances on Privacy Preserving Technologies and Solutions

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